

EMOTIONAL ALGORITHMICS

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Introduction

This essay has no clinical, psychological, or psychiatric pretensions, although references to biological or psychological processes are made in several paragraphs.

On the contrary, it is based on life experiences, most of them surprising, to which most people do not know how to react, or they do so impulsively, with the inherent consequences.

It is presented in principles, where it tries to explain in each case, the forms of understanding and suggestive reactions, taking as a starting point that every chain of actions behaves like an algorithm.

And when it comes to algorithms, there's a common thread that follows a pattern. And this pattern presents itself in similar forms in all people, since, ultimately, we are biologically made up of the same components.

What differentiates us is our character, which has a genetic origin, but with a greater impact, the environment of development and growth.

Our physical body has an intrinsic design, composed of various interconnected systems commanded by a central core: our brain.

One of these systems is the immune system, which operates autonomously, with a battalion of diverse defenses that keep dangerous organisms (viruses and/or bacteria) under control every minute, most of the time without us even realizing it.

However, this system doesn't consider the emotional impacts on the body. It addresses symptoms following stressors and external agents related to the bonds we establish with other people, but not how they impact our being.

As humanity, over time, increased contact between people and we grew as a species, bonds also increased exponentially.

With the advent of communication technologies, without regulations, without attachment, people today are more exposed to emotional impacts than in the past, where personal contact took place within a specific framework, in a limited anthroposphere.

Today, this anthroposphere goes beyond the physical to expand into the virtual, which has no limitations of time or space.

And this is where the risk of physical consequences, derived from the emotional consequences of interpersonal relationships, has increased.

We are disciplined subjects, as philosopher Byung-Chul Han explains, where the digital medium conditions us to react to the free will of global communication. And discipline is understood as the duty to react to all the information that comes through this channel.

These principles aim to provide strategies for the reactions that will inevitably arise, and behave as a defense system, the product of an acquired algorithmic sequence, in the face of the cruelty, indifference, apathy, and depersonalization to which we are exposed daily.

Creating your own Emotional Immune System.

Principle One: A Matter of Chemistry

The human brain is composed of special cells called neurons. The connection between each neuron is called a synapse.

Each neuron transmits information to its peers through the synapse, just as a smartphone uses radio waves to send and receive data.

This simple comparison is intended solely to illustrate that much of the communication between people through electronic devices already took place in every human brain.

Today, through digital communication, we have gradually lost the capacity for comprehensive interpretation that physical interaction once gave us.

Thousands of years ago, humans primarily integrated their understanding of their environment by combining their senses: sight, hearing, and smell.

The senses obtained data from the environment, which could be the communication emitted by another human being, and transmitted it to the brain through the eyes, nose, or ears.

This dataset formed a complex network of information, which the brain interpreted based on acquired experience (understanding spoken and gestural language) and processed possible outcomes based on its understanding of the entire set.

Thus, a sentence could be interpreted differently if body language demonstrated animosity, violence, or humor, even if the words were contrary.

Today, digital communication has limited the senses to real terms, and the brain, behaving as it developed throughout evolution, completes the interpretation by taking sections from previously lived experiences.

This process, adapted to modernity, increases emotional vulnerability, as it feeds on our own emotions and not those transmitted by the other subject.

This process is nothing more than a chain of chemical reactions. Once a group of neurons is activated in a certain situation, neurotransmitters appear, biomolecules responsible for sending instructions to the group of cells that make up the internal organs.

The main organs involved in emotions generate specific hormones linked to our sensations: adrenaline, oxytocin, dopamine, serotonin, cortisol, etc.

There are many studies and scientific evidence on so-called "emotional chemistry," which explain the various chemical combinations produced in our bodies in emotional situations. Therefore, we won't go into much technical detail here.

Through the limbic system, emotional reaction information reaches every part of our body.

Therefore, when faced with an unpleasant situation with another person, our gastrointestinal system is subsequently affected.

The common saying "I can't digest this" is literally just that: the body can't process what it ingests in such a way that it eliminates the toxic waste.

Emotions can't be eliminated like a swallowed hamburger.

They generate neuronal markers in our brain, which sometimes shuts down in an attempt to protect the rest of the body from their consequences.

But they're there, in our neural memory, and when a similar situation occurs in the present, that memory is activated and our body reacts physically.

Sensations such as anguish, fear, anxiety, restlessness, anger, and sadness are the result of the hormonal imbalance that occurs when interpreting a given situation.

It is the chemical consequence of a set of information received from the outside.

This composite block of information links with neuronal memory and triggers the entire process that determines the emotional reaction.

Explained as an algorithm, each part of the chemical process is part of a formula, a set of variables that are intrinsically integrated to produce a result. These variables can be understood as chain reactions.

If we could alter the content of each variable, the result would also be modified. If we had developed the ability to control the amount of oxytocin our brain demands, our fascination with another person would likely be less, and perhaps even reduce our stress levels caused by future disappointment.

Likewise, this same control would help us control adrenaline and react appropriately to injustice, abuse, or an unpleasant event.

Our own control over the content of the variables that make up the chemical algorithm determines the physical impact of emotions.

This is even true for those people who, due to their genetics, must resort to psychotropic drugs that assist in this process.

Studies on human behavior, on one's own feelings and their connection to the environment around them, have been a source of production for the pharmaceutical industry for many years.

The rise in levels of anxiety, fear, restlessness, and even panic has grown in recent years in proportion to the increase in digital communication.

Those who live in a completely analog world with little interpersonal contact probably require less effort to control the variables of the emotional chemical algorithm, compared to those who live in a large conglomerate, surrounded by communication technology.

Principle Two: Altering the Outcome

As described, algorithms are composed of variables. In mathematics, variables are usually expressed as letters. These letters are assigned a value, and a result is obtained. The algorithm $(a + b) + (c + d) = e$ could be represented as $(1 + 2) + (3 + 4) = 10$. If only one variable is altered, the result changes. So, for example, $(1 + 2) + (3 + 1) = 7$. Altering a single value, without modifying the algorithm, yields a different result.

Applied to the emotional field, the variables of the same algorithm could be represented as $(\text{person} + \text{pet}) + (\text{affection} + \text{care}) = \text{healthy pet/happy person}$.

Using the same principle of only changing one variable $(\text{person} + \text{pet}) + (\text{harm} + \text{neglect}) = \text{dead pet/unhappy person}$. While cruel, it also applies to human emotions.

The case could be $(\text{person} + \text{attraction}) + (\text{attention} + \text{commitment}) = \text{pairing}$. The result obtained is satisfying, there is an increase in oxytocin, and the person feels pleasure.

Conversely, the case $(\text{person} + \text{attraction}) + (\text{neglect} + \text{indifference}) = \text{frustration}$. Cortisol increases, oxytocin decreases. Frustration implies anxiety, fear, sadness, and disappointment.

All of these emotions combined point to depression. Dopamine production abruptly drops. A depressed person loses interest in everyday life and in themselves.

Their mood has a physical impact, producing listlessness and a lack of willpower, energy, and drive. Adrenaline levels decrease.

The human brain functions consciously with two factors: the rational factor and the emotional factor.

The rational factor is applied by logic, and logic is applied by acquired knowledge. Rationality is acquired by incorporating data, whether experienced or learned.

Logic is relatively simple. It is deduced by right or wrong. It is based on four fundamental laws: identity (one thing cannot be another), non-contradiction (a thing cannot be both true and false at the same time), the excluded middle (a thing can be true or false, with no other option), and sufficient reason (a thing is the way it is for a reason, cause, or circumstance).

Logic underpins rationality. And rationality balances emotions. A person is considered "balanced" when, both rationally and emotionally, they fall within the so-called "neurotypical" parameters.

People who experience emotional disturbances have difficulty rationalizing them. The counterbalance to emotion is reason, and sometimes this balance malfunctions.

In many cases, they turn to elements external to themselves, through therapists and psychotropic drugs. These act as a supplement to reason, to contain emotions within neurotypical ranges.

If they learned to modify the variables of emotional algorithms, they could incorporate a variable "r," assigned to rationality. Thus, an increase in the value of "r" would apply additional weight to the emotional algorithm, reducing the risk of an undesirable outcome.

Returning to the algorithm cited above, $(\text{person} + \text{attraction}) + (\text{inattention} + \text{indifference})$, the variable "reason" could be added, which would drastically change the algorithm to $(\text{person} + \text{attraction}) + (\text{inattention} + \text{indifference}) + \text{reason} = ?$.

The symbol "?" raises questions. That is, the outcome is not fully defined until the reason is substantiated by logic. Any of the aforementioned Laws of Logic apply to substantiate reason, and this influences the emotional outcome.

However, there are people who, despite therapy and psychotropic drugs, tend to form distorted logic to adapt reason and thus substantiate their emotional impulses.

First and foremost, we must consider the individual's development, where marks are left in the neuronal memory that lead them to repeat cycles. This way, they reiterate patterns acquired during their development, normalizing them, incorporating them as habitual, even despite the social rejection and psychological damage it causes. They verbalize them, but they don't increase the value of reason to such an extent that it changes the outcome. Incorporating, rooting in conscious memory, the fact that the variable "reason" provides the necessary weight to compensate for the emotional burden, allows us to adapt the output of the emotional algorithm required under certain circumstances, with more tolerable results.

Principle Three: Causes and Consequences

Isaac Newton's Third Law of Motion states that "for every action (force) in nature, there is an equal and opposite reaction."

Also known as the Law of Action and Reaction, it can be understood as when an object in a state of stillness only resists a force that attempts to remove it from that state.

The cause of its movement involves the reaction of resistance, until it is set in motion, the consequence of which is to move from one point to another.

It is a way of illustrating that every action inherently carries a consequence. And actions in people are expressed through actions and words.

Actions are mechanical movements to accomplish something, and words are the expression of ideas or emotions.

Both actions and words can be based on reason or emotion. Actions motivated by rationality, for example, are logical and therefore rational to use the handle to open a door, but they can also be justified emotionally, given that opening the door leads to a pleasant surprise on the other side.

Either way, the cause has a consequence. Opening the door can imply a pleasant emotion or disappointment.

Therefore, the variables of cause and consequence also influence the emotional algorithm. And they become more relevant when the causes involve people other than the protagonist. In the algorithm cited in principle two, reason was incorporated to balance the emotional impulse.

Incorporating the variables of cause and consequence involves reinforcing reason in order to balance emotions.

Considering consequences opens up endless questions and assumptions, given that no one knows the future. You can only risk an outcome based on similar experiences.

If closing a door without removing your hand means hurting your fingers, the next time you close a door, you'll be careful not to leave your fingers exposed. The pain on your fingers will fix the event in your neural memory, and in similar future cases, your brain will automatically sound the alarm, slightly increasing adrenaline to attract attention at that moment, just as you close the door.

Thus, reason, from a logical perspective, must support the cause, and the consequences must be consistent with logic, reason, and cause. If this line is assembled solely by emotions, the consequences will most likely not be as desired.

Emotions are not based on logic or reason. They are impulses composed of an irrational set of synapses, which indicate the excessive increase of certain hormones.

But within irrationality, the algorithm also applies. The irrational can be a sum of various unconventional variables, irrational in their unity, whose values are dystopian.

The brain knows the limits imposed by development, by learning. If a person developed without moral or ethical limits, they would learn, through cause and consequence, their physical limitations, even at the cost of their death.

For example, if they felt the impulse to fly, when humans don't have wings. At best, the fall could cause physical damage, and they would feel emotionally frustrated.

But the human brain is a whole, not a group of independent brains. Everything is connected within, and from there all the rest of the functioning of the human body begins.

While part of the brain is autonomously responsible for keeping it functioning, the rest is available for consciousness. And this is governed by reason and emotion.

The development of thinking increases as data is incorporated. And the data set becomes information.

Each piece of data could be applied as a value to a variable, and the combination of variables into processable information. In other words, an algorithm.

The reason for incorporating data is vital to a person's development. And the consequences of this are their actions and expressions.

Genetic inheritance can influence abilities that are more prominent than others. Thus, some people draw very well, naturally, but are out of tune when singing. While others are fine-tuned, but have poor handwriting.

Similarly, genetic inheritance can predispose a person to be more emotional than others. That is, to express their emotions more openly through gestures and words.

All people possess both rationality and emotionality. The circumstances of development, the environment they grow up in, and the social context provide additional information so that one aspect or another becomes more prominent than the other, or remains in balance.

Just because a person doesn't express their emotions openly doesn't mean they don't experience them. Various external reasons may have shaped their rationality to the point where they contain their emotions, even if they suffer them in silence.

Today's society, disciplined by open expression, with or without justifiable reason, somewhat condemns a lack of emotion. Especially in digital communication, emotional expressions are highly valued, as they also awaken memorized emotions in the recipient.

It's a risk for the person to expose their emotions to the global community, unless it's as a plea for help in an extreme case.

Such exposure has consequences. Often, they are exploited by the cruelty of others or manipulated against the sender.

Because people are formed with different aspects based on the development of thought.

Humans are the only animals that can be cruel without reason. The remaining species fulfill their survival role: they are either prey or predators. They do not kill or harm for any reason other than the survival and continuity of the species.

People have evolved beyond the basic "run or be eaten" principle, but with consequences without rational causes.

In cases of abuse or cruelty, the emotional algorithm has variables outside the general limits, but so deeply rooted that the person is convinced that their combination is correct. Faced with undeniable reality, they may temporarily accept that their variables do not contain coherent values.

The consequences of others accepting these out-of-range values are counterproductive, both for the individual and for their environment. And sometimes, life-threatening.

It is important, then, to keep in mind that the algorithm's framework must be coherent, with its variables balanced between reason, logic, and emotion, which will support the causes and justify the consequences.

Principle Four: The War Machine

All living beings have defenses. Insects generally have an exoskeleton that protects their soft organs, like armor.

Others developed spines or prickles on their skin, as well as thick layers of fat, or thick fur that protects them from the elements and attacks.

Over time, the human species has lost some of these qualities. Today, we have no external protection whatsoever, except for those we create thanks to our brains, our thoughts, our ideas.

But not all risks are visible to the naked eye.

There are a huge number of microscopic organisms that are harmful to humans and enter the body through various routes. Some live inside us from birth.

This complex is composed mostly of bacteria, but also viruses and spores. A biological conglomerate that is constantly attacking humans.

To counteract this, the human species has perfected a relentless mechanism: the immune system. This impressive war machine wages minute-by-minute battles against any foreign body that invades the body.

Like a multidisciplinary army, the immune system is composed of phagocytes (cells that literally devour the invader), neutrophils (the rapid response squad for initial containment of the attack), macrophages (larger cells that ingest pathogens and dead cells and stimulate other immune cells, even reporting their composition to record the enemy's characteristics), monocytes (something like the trainers of combatants), and dendrites (the intelligence and development group for specific defenses), among others.

This formidable group works in a synchronized manner and repels any internal attack, efficiently and autonomously.

The person doesn't need to consciously announce an attack or an invader. The war machine explores every corner of the body on its own, and when faced with a risk, it activates its entire defense protocol and is expeditious. However, sometimes its defenses are breached, as enemies become increasingly skilled.

In the past, suffering (symptoms experienced when the immune system enters a major battle) had to be endured stoically.

Nowadays, the pharmaceutical industry has reduced this suffering through painkillers or chemical compounds that enhance the immune system's power of action.

The war machine also attempts to react to the effects of emotional damage, but it only responds to potential organ damage when the precursor to the battle is the person themselves. In the face of emotional damage, depressive symptoms generally manifest, disrupting the entire body, including the immune system. Commands are unclear, and different battle fronts arise, from muscle tension to gastrointestinal problems, resulting in chaos and confusion.

The immune system is overwhelmed and confused.

Psychopharmacology has provided several solutions based on the characteristics it has been able to standardize over the years, but not all humans respond the same way.

Therefore, in general, the use of additional chemicals is always a matter of trial and error. And like any combination of chemicals, these also have consequences. This implies another set of chemicals to address the "side effects."

The war machine is also based on algorithms, following a logical pattern: once an invader is detected, it calls in the army of combat cells, reporting the exact location of the battle.

The bloodstream is the logistics that quickly mobilizes troops to the scene, and according to intelligence reports, reinforces the attack with specific elements.

Along the way, it can be equipped with chemical auxiliaries supplied from abroad. It's like receiving a temporary upgrade over the available equipment.

If the reason for mobilizing the war machine is emotional, the situation is completely different. Internal chaos, as mentioned, creates confusion, and it is unclear to the battalions which battle fronts they are facing.

This situation is an advantage for organisms that routinely attempt to invade the human body, and they show no mercy. This is how ailments manifest that, under other circumstances, would never have been reported.

Ulcers, dermatitis, alopecia, headaches, and muscle spasms are some of the symptoms that arise when emotional factors become harmful.

Faced with these, the person seeks medical specialists seeking assistance for the battle they feel they are waging.

Today's medical practice has evolved and no longer focuses solely on the symptoms expressed, but also explores other possible causes.

Thus, you can deduce that the origin of the problem isn't just a virus or a bacteria: there are initial triggers that have led to the great battle.

Clinical medicine, in conjunction with pharmacology, also complies with algorithms, following established protocols thanks to the record of successes over time. Although almost the same number of failures are also recorded along the way.

These treatment algorithms, known as protocols, assume a result, a consequence: a healthy person. However, often the ailment is attenuated, even disappears, but the cause that caused it is only temporarily numbed.

Fifth Principle: The Emotional Immune System

As clarified in the introduction, this document is an essay based solely on life experiences.

It is not intended to be a medical treatise, for any of its specialties: clinical or psychiatric.

Just as the human body has an immune system responsible for keeping it healthy, one could conceivably consider a system that addresses the precursors that affect the body through its emotions.

Since the application of algorithms is a proven method, it could be understood that developing algorithms to balance emotions would work.

While the principle of development is closely linked to logic and rationality, where emotions seem to have no place, ultimately, everything is learning.

When a human being is born, their emotions are linked only to their development. They express themselves through crying, a natural way of getting attention, given that they are not accustomed to hunger pangs or simply the growth of their body.

As time goes by, they incorporate data about their environment and those they interact with.

They learn visual and verbal communication, and thus, they also learn to distinguish emotions.

With the increase in relationships with other people, new information, new variables, new logic, new reasoning, and new emotions appear.

It forms a series of algorithms that grant it a place in its anthroposphere.

Depending on genetic characteristics and the environment in which it grew up, human beings shape their personality. They create variables that shape their relational algorithms.

This is learning. Consequently, it could also develop algorithms useful for emotional management.

During schooling, they encounter other human beings in the same conditions: incorporating knowledge and developing their algorithms.

Conventional education dictates standards of ethics and morals according to the era. Good and evil become somewhat blurred.

Adolescence and the onset of adulthood bring with them another wealth of information and an increased emotional impact. Disappointment is experienced as if it were the end of the world.

As adults, taking on responsibilities and commitments generates more emotional tension.

Interpersonal relationships, in social, family, or work environments, add variables whose values can increase or decrease drastically, altering the results of the applied algorithm, even without finding the rational cause that caused such changes.

Rationality and logic give way to excessive emotions, and the consequences are not always easy to accept.

Only physical damage can be measured as aggressive, based on the visible result. But emotional damage is recorded in neuronal memory and hidden from view.

An emotional immune system would mitigate the side effects produced by non-physical aggression.

To develop a system of these characteristics, it is important to enhance reason and logic.

Ultimately, a system is a set of interrelated and interdependent elements that function as an organized whole to achieve a common goal or purpose.

Logic itself is independent. It is based on four principles already mentioned, regardless of the context.

Rationality is the effect of the application of logic. It is not dependent, but rather reinforces its foundation.

The principle of action and reaction is consistent with logic and rationality. It becomes cause and consequence depending on the action.

Therefore, an algorithm could be developed to describe the emotional immune system as follows:

1. Beginning of the Emotional Process

Emotional Trigger Entry

- **Detect Event:** The person encounters a situation, thought, or interaction (internal or external)
- **Type of Stimulus:** Is it perceived as positive, negative, or neutral?
 - If positive or neutral: Normal process of emotional well-being.
 - If negative (potential "emotional pathogen"): Activate the Threat Detection System.

2. Threat Detection System

Initial Recognition:

(Recommended practice: writing the situation allows for the classification of the event)

- **Assess Intensity:** How strong is the initial emotional reaction (e.g., hexadecimal base metric scale from 0 to F)?
- **Identify the Dominant Emotion:** fear, sadness, anger, anxiety, guilt, frustration, etc.
- **Filtered by Experience:**
 - Is it a known or recurring threat? (Long-term emotional memory).
 - Are there established response patterns?

3. Response Mechanisms

(best practice: color-code the intensity of the threat level)

Beginning of Emotional Defenses

- **Threat level is Mild/Moderate:**
 - **Self-regulation:** Activate internal coping mechanisms.
 - * **Conscious Breathing:** Trying to calm the body.
 - * **Cognitive Restructuring:** Challenging Negative Thoughts.
 - * **Positive Distraction:** Redirecting Attention.
 - * **Mild Social Connection:** Seeking minimal support.
 - * **Controlled Emotional Expression:** Allowing yourself to feel without getting overwhelmed.
 - **Self-regulation result:**
 - * Success: Reduction of negative emotional intensity. Return to "Normal Well-being".
 - * Failure: Persistent or increasing negative emotion. Escalate to "Severe Threat."
- **Threat level is Severe or self-regulation failed:**
 - **Activation of Support Networks ("Neutrophils"):**
 - * Active Communication: Talking with trusted friends, family, and partners.
 - * Seeking Professional Advice: Therapists, medical clinics.
 - * Therapeutic Activities: Hobbies, exercise, and the outdoors.
 - * Setting Boundaries: Personal space and time.
 - **Active Problem Management ("Phagocytes"):**
 - * Conflict Resolution: Directly confront the source of the threat.
 - * Decision-Making: Concrete and sustained actions to change the situation.

* Radical Acceptance: If the problem has no solution, incorporate it as part of the learning process and coexist with acceptance.

4. Recovery and Memory Phase (Immunity)

Restoration of Balance

- **Decreased Intensity:** The negative emotion is attenuated.
- **Return to Well-being:** Returning to a more neutral or positive emotional state.

Learning and Strengthening

- **Post-Event Analysis:** Fixing the event and its outcome in the neural memory.
- **Strategy Adaptation:** Adjusting successful and unsuccessful actions.
- **Creating an Emotional Memory Bank:**
 - **Prevention:** When faced with a similar threat in the future, the response will be faster, more efficient, and more resilient.
 - **Consolidation:** Greater emotional resilience is built.

5. Monitoring and Maintenance

Regular Self-Assessment: emotional state check.

Preventive Practices

- Self-care habits: sleep, nutrition, exercise, leisure.
- Healthy social interactions.
- Development of emotional intelligence.

6. End of Cycle / Recycling

- If recovery and learning are achieved, the system returns to a monitoring state, ready for the next stimulus.
- If the system becomes overloaded or repeatedly fails to recover, the need for external intervention or significant adjustment of strategies is indicated.

Final Contribution: Emotional Algebra

The algorithm developed in the Fifth Principle can be expressed using mathematics. The algebraic expression could be written as:

$$RE = f(I_{EE}, E_{EA}, AP)$$

Where:

RE: Emotional Resilience Level (how quickly or effectively a person recovers). A higher score indicates greater resilience..

I_{EE}: Intensity of the Negative Emotional Stimulus (the emotional “event” or “threat”). A higher value indicates a more challenging stimulus..

E_{EA}: Effectiveness of Coping Strategies (the quality and appropriateness of the emotional regulation tools used). A higher score indicates greater effectiveness..

AP: Learning from Previous Experiences (the "memory" and adaptation of the system). A higher value indicates that more has been learned and the system is more prepared..

If a relationship is established between resilience and the intensity of the emotional event, the first being inversely proportional to the second, and directly proportional to the effectiveness of the system's strategies, it could be expressed as follows::

$$RE = k \cdot \frac{E_{EA} \cdot AP}{I_{EE}}$$

Where:

k It is a positive constant that represents the neurotypical basis of a person's emotional disposition.

So:

If *I_{EE}* increases (greater threat) => *RE* decreases, meaning resilience is more challenged and recovery is more difficult.

If *E_{EA}* increases (more effective strategies) => *RE* increases, facilitating recovery.

If *AP* increases (more learning/experience) => *RE* increases, which implies that the system is more efficient in handling future similar threats.

As final considerations, the development of an Emotional Immune System can be conceived as long as the person is predisposed to learning and incorporating into their neuronal memory the processes (algorithms) that strengthen their reactions to external or internal stimuli, and control the range of emotional impact on their life.

The algebraic development of the proposed approach serves as a standardized monitor of a person's emotional experiences, with the sole purpose of providing a rational explanation for the consequences arising from triggering events.

It should be considered that certain variables are qualitative, so each person will be able to establish a level of numerical expression, depending on how they rate the intensity, effectiveness and quality (stimulus, strategies, learning).